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Work Package 3 - Chinese Policy on the Rule of Law and Its Implementation - Deliverable 3.2 – Summary of Analysed Sources

For the purposes of this analysis, a total of 364 Mandarin Chinese documents discussing the rule of law, published between 2012 and 2022, were selected. These documents were freely accessible on official Chinese websites, including those of the Communist Party of China (CCP), the National People's Congress (NPC), and the State Council Information Office (SCIO). The corpus comprises a diverse range of text formats, including short news reports, policy announcements, annual reports, press conferences, and opinion pieces.

Initially, the plan was to include ten documents per year. However, to ensure a comprehensive analysis, all available texts on the CCP, NPC, and SCIO websites were considered. It's important to note that a substantial portion of these documents reiterate key policy announcements and documents, which will be discussed in more detail later in this document. Nevertheless, these documents also display a high level of repetitiveness in their content. The wording and phraseology in the selected documents reflect the original Chinese texts and represent the message aimed at the Chinese public.

While the documents might suggest that the primary goal of the Chinese government is to reduce arbitrariness, increase efficiency, and enhance the professionalism of the judiciary, as well as the legal knowledge and education of the public, this would only be partially true. The Party-state seeks to tighten the administration to preserve and enhance the Party's authority with Xi Jinping at its core. These reforms could create legal certainty for a significant portion of the Chinese population in non-sensitive cases. However, the Chinese government is selectively adopting certain characteristics of the rule of law, while others, such as the separation of powers or the supremacy of law, remain absent.

The documents also stress the importance of modern technologies such as big data, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence in building a "smart rule of law." The rule of law build-up in China is not solely inward-looking but also has implications for the rest of the world. Based on the Plan for the Construction of a Rule of Law China (2020–2025), China should actively participate in developing international norms, promote a fair and equitable international rules-based system, and accelerate the development of a legal framework applicable beyond Chinese borders. It aims to promote a Chinese interpretation of the rule of law internationally. As a global power, China believes it should have a voice in shaping or reshaping existing norms, including those related to the rule of law. This aspect will be a central focus of the following Work Package 4: Chinese Outputs on the International Scene.

For better orientation, this document also includes a list of main events, including the (Plenary) Sessions of the Central Committee of the CCP and the National People's Congress. The list of all documents can be accessed here: Lavička, M. (2024). Chinese Policy on the Rule of Law and Its Implementation WP3 - list of analyzed sources [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13132493>. These resources will be used as a base to generate new open-access content.

Selected key events

2012

The 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China marked a significant shift towards strengthening the rule of law. Xi Jinping emphasized the importance of governing the country according to the law, setting the stage for comprehensive legal reforms.

2013

The Third Plenary Session of the 18th CCP Central Committee adopted a decision on major issues concerning comprehensively deepening reforms, including significant measures to improve the legal system and enhance judicial independence.

2014

The Fourth Plenary Session of the 18th CCP Central Committee was dedicated to the rule of law, a first in the party's history. It outlined a blueprint for building a socialist rule of law system with Chinese characteristics. It also proposed governing the internet according to law 《依法治网》. The CCP Central Committee issued the Decision concerning Several Major Issues in Comprehensively Advancing Governance According to Law 《中共中央关于全面推进依法治国若干重大问题的决定》.

2015

The National People's Congress (NPC) passed several important laws, including the National Security Law and the Anti-Terrorism Law, aimed at strengthening national security and public safety within the legal framework. CCP Central Committee and the State Council issued the Implementation Outline for the Construction of a Law-Based Government (2015-2020) 《法治政府建设实施纲要（2015—2020年）》.

2016

The NPC Standing Committee adopted the Charity Law, which regulated charitable organizations and activities. According to the government, the reason for this law was to promote transparency and accountability in the sector. However, the critics stress the emphasis on control instead of openness.

2017

The 19th National Congress of the CCP reiterated the importance of the rule of law. It introduced the concept of Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era 《习近平新时代中国特色社会主义思想》, which includes legal reforms as a critical component.

2018

The Constitution was amended to include Xi Jinping Thought, and the Supervision Law was enacted, establishing a new anti-corruption body, the National Supervisory Commission 《国家监察委员会》.

2019

The Foreign Investment Law was passed, providing a more transparent and predictable legal environment for foreign investors, aligning with international standards. The General Office of the CCP Central Committee and the General Office of the State Council issued the Regulations on Supervision of the Construction of a Rule of Law Government and the Implementation of Responsibilities 《法治政府建设与责任落实督察工作规定》.

2020

The Civil Code, China's first comprehensive civil code, was adopted, codifying various civil laws into a single document to better protect citizens' rights and interests. Between 16 and 17 November, the Central Conference on Comprehensively Promoting the Rule of Law 《中央全面依法治国工作会议》 took place in Beijing with Xi Jinping and Li Keqiang delivering their speeches. On 7 December, the Central Committee of the CCP issued the Outline for Building a Rule of Law Society (2020–2025) 《法治社会建设实施纲要（2020—2025年）》.

2021

The NPC adopted the Personal Information Protection Law, which set strict guidelines for the collection, use, and storage of personal data, enhancing privacy protections. The Central Committee of the CCP issued a Plan for the Construction of a Rule of Law China (2020–2025) 《法治中国建设规划(2020—2025年)》 and together with the State Council the Outline for

the Implementation of a Rule of Law Government (2021-2025) 《法治政府建设实施纲要（2021—2025年）》. With the Outline from 2020, these three documents form the so-called One Plan and Two Outlines 《一规划两纲要》. Another document issued by the State Council together with the Central Committee of the CCP is the Opinions Regarding the Strengthening of the Socialist Rule of Law Culture 《关于加强社会主义法治文化建设的意见》. The State Administration for Market Regulation issued the Outline for the Implementation of Market Supervision under the Rule of Law (2021–2025) 《法治市场监管建设实施纲要（2021—2025年）》.

2022

The 20th National Congress of the Communist Party of China started its first Plenary Session. Xi Jinping's Thought on the Rule of Law was presented as a combination of basic principles of Marxism with China's specific reality and China's excellent traditional culture. China Banking and Insurance Regulatory Commission issued the National Implementation Programme for Building the Rule of Law in the Banking and Insurance Sector 《全国银行业保险业法治建设实施方案》.

Table 1 List of (Plenary) Sessions of the Central Committee of the CCP and National People's Congress (NPC) during the examined period

CENTRAL COMMITTEE OF THE CCP		National People's Congress	
17th Central Committee of the CCP		11th NPC	2008–2013
7 th Plenary Session	1–4 November 2012	5 th Session	March 2012
18th Central Committee of the CCP			
1 st Plenary Session	15 November 2012		
2 nd Plenary Session	26–28 February 2013	12th NPC	2013–2018
3 rd Plenary Session	9–12 November 2013	1 st Session	March 2013
4 th Plenary Session	20–23 October 2014	2 nd Session	March 2014
5 th Plenary Session	26–29 October 2015	3 rd Session	March 2015
6 th Plenary Session	24–27 October 2016	4 th Session	March 2016
7 th Plenary Session	11–14 October 2017	5 th Session	March 2017
19th Central Committee of the CCP			
1 st Plenary Session	25 October 2017		
2 nd Plenary Session	18–19 January 2018	13th NPC	2018–2023
3 rd Plenary Session	26–28 February 2018	1 st Session	March 2018
4 th Plenary Session	28–31 October 2019	2 nd Session	March 2019
5 th Plenary Session	26–29 October 2020	3 rd Session	May 2020
6 th Plenary Session	8–11 November 2021	4 th Session	March 2021
7 th Plenary Session	9–12 October 2022	5 th Session	March 2022
20th Central Committee of the CCP			
1 st Plenary Session	23 October 2022		

Source: Baidu, Gov.cn

DOCUMENTS

CCP Central Committee Decision Concerning Several Major Issues in Comprehensively Advancing Governance According to Law 《中共中央关于全面推进依法治国若干重大问题的决定》

This document was passed on 23 October 2014 at the 4th Plenary Session of the 18th Central Committee of the Chinese Communist Party. The planned measures are aimed at creating a more robust legal framework to support China's development and governance.

1. **Establishing a Socialist Rule of Law System:** building a socialist rule of law system with Chinese characteristics, ensuring that the law is respected and strictly enforced
2. **Improving Legislation:** improving the legislative process to make laws more scientific, democratic, and aligned with the needs of the people by addressing issues like departmentalization and faction wars in legislative work
3. **Strengthening Law Enforcement:** highlighting the importance of strict law enforcement and judicial fairness, addressing problems such as selective law enforcement, judicial corruption, and lack of transparency
4. **Enhancing Legal Awareness:** focusing on increasing legal awareness among the public and officials, e.g. about the idea that everyone should respect, learn, and use the law
5. **Judicial Reforms:** reforming the judicial system to ensure independence and fairness by including measures to prevent interference in judicial processes and to improve the professionalism of judicial personnel
6. **Party Leadership:** reaffirming the leadership of the Communist Party in advancing the rule of law, ensuring that the Party's policies and decisions are implemented through legal means

Outline for the Construction of a Law-Based Government (2015-2020) 《法治政府建设实施纲要（2015—2020年）》

This document lists several key objectives and principles for advancing the rule of law in government administration in China. It was announced by the Central Committee of the CCP and the State Council on 27 December 2015 and issued in the State Council Gazette no. 1 《中华人民共和国国务院公报》 on 10 January 2016. The main points include:

- 1. Guiding Ideology:** The document emphasizes the importance of adhering to the leadership of the Communist Party of China and the principles of socialism with Chinese characteristics. It aims to fully implement the spirit of the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China and subsequent plenary sessions.
- 2. Overall Goals:** By 2020, the goal was to establish a scientifically functional government, legally defined in its powers and responsibilities, strictly law-abiding, open and transparent, clean and efficient, and trusted by the public.
- 3. Basic Principles:**
 - upholding the leadership of the Communist Party of China
 - ensuring the people's principal status
 - guaranteeing equality before the law
 - combining the rule of law with the rule of virtue
 - adapting to China's actual conditions
 - governing according to the Constitution and laws
 - simplifying administration and decentralizing power
- 4. Essential Tasks and Measures:**
 - **Fully Performing Government Functions:** separating government from enterprises, capital, public institutions, and social organizations and optimizing services
 - **Improving the Legal System for Government Administration:** enhancing the quality of government legislation and ensuring that all administrative actions are based on law

- **Promoting Scientific, Democratic, and Law-Based Decision-Making:** establishing sound decision-making mechanisms that involve public participation, expert consultation, and risk assessment
- **Strict, Fair, and Civilized Law Enforcement:** strengthening the enforcement of laws and regulations, ensuring that all enforcement actions are legal, fair, and transparent
- **Enhancing Public Services:** improving the quality and efficiency of public services and ensuring equal access to essential public services
- **Strengthening Supervision and Accountability:** establishing mechanisms for supervising administrative power and holding officials accountable for their actions

Regulations on Supervision of the Construction of a Rule of Law Government and the Implementation of Responsibilities 《法治政府建设与责任落实督察工作规定》

The Central Committee of the Chinese Communist Party, together with the State Council, issued these Regulations on 15 April 2019 to strengthen the leadership of the Communist Party in building a law-based government, ensuring that government actions are in line with the law and promoting accountability at all levels. These Regulations are formulated in accordance with the Decision concerning Several Major Issues in Comprehensively Advancing Governance According to Law and the Outline for the Construction of a Law-Based Government (2015-2020).

1. **Scope:** The regulations apply to local party committees, governments, and departments above the county level, focusing on their efforts to build a law-based government.
2. **Supervision Content:** The supervision covers various aspects, including the implementation of legal frameworks, administrative decision-making processes, law enforcement, and the promotion of legal awareness among government officials.
3. **Responsibilities:** Local party and government leaders are held accountable for promoting the construction of a law-based government within their jurisdictions, which includes integrating legal principles into economic and social development plans.
4. **Methods of Supervision:** The regulations specify methods such as written reports, on-site inspections, and third-party evaluations to ensure compliance and effectiveness.

5. **Reporting and Accountability:** Annual reports on the progress of building a law-based government are required, and there are mechanisms for holding officials accountable for failures or misconduct.

2020 Conference on Work Related to Overall Law-Based Governance 《中央全面依法治国工作会议》

During the Central Conference on Work Related to Overall Law-based Governance on 17 November 2020, Xi Jinping delivered a speech emphasizing the need to promote the socialist rule of law with Chinese characteristics.

1. **Establishment of Xi Jinping Thought on the Rule of Law:**

- The conference marked the establishment of Xi Jinping Thought on the Rule of Law as the guiding principle for law-based governance in China. This thought addresses major questions about why and how law-based governance should be advanced, adapting Marxist theories on the rule of law to the Chinese context.

2. **“11 Upholds” 《十一个坚持》:**

- Xi Jinping outlined 11 fundamental principles, known as the “11 upholds,” which include:
 1. upholding Party leadership on overall law-based governance
 2. taking a people-centred approach
 3. staying on the path of the socialist rule of law with Chinese characteristics
 4. adhering to Constitution-based governance
 5. promoting the modernization of China’s governance system and capacity along the path of the rule of law
 6. adhering to a system of the socialist rule of law with Chinese characteristics
 7. pursuing coordinated progress in law-based governance, law-based exercise of state power, and law-based government administration, as well as promoting the integrated development of the rule of law for the country, the government, and society

8. ensuring sound lawmaking, strict law enforcement, impartial administration of justice, and the observance of the law by everyone
9. taking a coordinated approach to promoting the rule of law at home and in matters involving foreign parties
10. fostering a high-quality team of professionals with both integrity and ability for legal work
11. ensuring that leading officials at various levels faithfully implement major decisions and plans made by the CCP Central Committee on overall law-based governance

Outline for Building a Rule of Law Society (2020–2025) 《法治社会建设实施纲要（2020 - 2025 年）》

The document was issued by the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on 7 December 2020. It outlines China’s strategic plan to enhance the rule of law. The key takeaways include:

1. **Guiding Ideology:** The document emphasizes the importance of adhering to Marxism-Leninism, Mao Zedong Thought, Deng Xiaoping Theory, the “Three Represents,” the Scientific Outlook on Development, and Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era. It aims to integrate these ideologies into the construction of a rule of law society.
2. **Key Principles:** It highlights principles such as the centralized and unified leadership of the Party, the people-centred approach, equality before the law, and the integration of the rule of law, rule of virtue, and self-governance.
3. **Overall Goals:** By 2025, the plan aims to complete the “Eighth Five-Year Plan” for law popularisation, deeply embed the rule of law in society, and significantly improve the legal system and social governance, setting the foundation for achieving a rule-of-law society by 2035.
4. **Promotion of Legal Awareness:** The document stresses the importance of enhancing legal awareness among all citizens, promoting respect for the Constitution, and ensuring that the rule of law becomes a fundamental social consensus.

5. **Strengthening Legal Education:** The Outline calls for comprehensive legal education, mainly targeting youth, government officials, and the general public, to foster a culture of lawfulness.
6. **Improving Legal Systems:** The plan includes enhancing legislation in key social areas such as education, healthcare, social security, and environmental protection, ensuring that laws are fair, just, and effectively implemented.
7. **Enhancing Judicial Fairness:** The Outline emphasizes the need for judicial reforms to ensure fairness, transparency, and efficiency in the judicial process, protecting citizens' rights and interests.
8. **Public Legal Services:** The document outlines the development of a modern public legal service system that is accessible, efficient, and equitable, ensuring that all citizens can obtain timely and effective legal assistance.
9. **Social Governance:** It promotes the integration of legal, moral, and social norms to create a harmonious and orderly society, encouraging public participation in social governance.
10. **Implementation and Supervision:** The Outline calls for the establishment of mechanisms to ensure the effective implementation and supervision of the outlined goals involving various levels of government and society.

Plan for the Construction of a Rule of Law China (2020-2025) 《法治中国建设规划(2020 - 2025 年)》

The Central Committee of the Communist Party of China issued the plan on 10 January 2021. It outlines China's strategic plan to enhance the rule of law. Here are the key points:

1. **Guiding Ideology:** The plan emphasizes adherence to Marxism-Leninism, Mao Zedong Thought, Deng Xiaoping Theory, the "Three Represents," the Scientific Outlook on Development, and Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era. It aims to integrate these ideologies into the construction of a rule of law society.
2. **Primary Principles:** Key principles include the centralized and unified leadership of the Party, a people-centred approach, equality before the law, and the integration of the rule of law, the rule of virtue, and self-governance.

3. **Overall Goals:** By 2025, the plan aims to complete the “Eighth Five-Year Plan” for law popularisation, deeply embed the rule of law in society, and significantly improve the legal system and social governance. This sets the foundation for achieving a rule-of-law society by 2035.
4. **Promotion of Legal Awareness:** The document stresses the importance of enhancing legal awareness among all citizens, promoting respect for the Constitution, and ensuring that the rule of law becomes a fundamental social consensus.
5. **Strengthening Legal Education:** Comprehensive legal education is emphasized, mainly targeting youth, government officials, and the general public, to foster a culture of lawfulness.
6. **Improving Legal Systems:** The plan includes enhancing legislation in key social areas such as education, healthcare, social security, and environmental protection, ensuring that laws are fair, just, and effectively implemented.
7. **Enhancing Judicial Fairness:** Judicial reforms are highlighted to ensure fairness, transparency, and efficiency in the judicial process, protecting citizens’ rights and interests.
8. **Public Legal Services:** The development of a modern public legal service system that is accessible, efficient, and equitable is outlined, ensuring that all citizens can obtain timely and effective legal assistance.
9. **Social Governance:** The plan promotes the integration of legal, moral, and social norms to create a harmonious and orderly society, encouraging public participation in social governance.
10. **Implementation and Supervision:** Mechanisms are to be established to ensure the effective implementation and supervision of the outlined goals involving various levels of government and society.

Opinions Regarding the Strengthening of the Socialist Rule of Law Culture 《关于加强社会主义法治文化的意见》

This document was issued by the General Office of the Central Committee of the CCP together with the General Office of the State Council on 5 April 2021.

1. **Guiding Ideology:**

- Xi Jinping's Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era
- Integrating socialist core values into the legal culture

2. **Work Principles:**

- **Party Leadership:** ensuring the Party's leadership in all aspects of law-based governance
- **People-Centred Approach:** focusing on the needs and interests of the people
- **Integration of Law and Morality:** combining legal governance with moral education

3. **Main Tasks:**

- **Promoting Xi Jinping's Thought on the Rule of Law:** deepening the study and dissemination of Xi Jinping's legal theories
- **Enhancing Legal Education:** incorporating legal education into the national education system, especially targeting youth and public officials
- **Strengthening Constitutional Awareness:** promoting the spirit of the Constitution and ensuring its implementation

4. **Cultural Integration:**

- **Traditional Legal Culture:** revitalizing traditional Chinese legal culture and integrating it with modern practices
- **Legal Art and Media:** encouraging the creation of legal-themed art and media to promote legal awareness

5. **Infrastructure Development:**

- **Legal Culture Bases:** establishing legal culture bases and integrating legal elements into public spaces
- **Digital Legal Culture:** promoting the digitalization of legal culture through online platforms and resources

6. **International Cooperation:**

- **Global Legal Exchange:** enhancing international cooperation and exchanges in legal culture
- **Belt and Road Initiative:** utilizing the Belt and Road Initiative to promote legal culture and cooperation with other countries

Outline for the Implementation of a Rule of Law Government (2021-2025) 《法治政府建设实施纲要（2021—2025年）》

The Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council issued this Outline on 11 August 2021. This document is noteworthy for several reasons: it clarifies the guiding principles for building the rule of law in China, outlines the stages of this development, and envisions the global impact of the Chinese version of the rule of law.

In the first section, this document lists the **guiding principles**. Among them are:

1. insisting on the centralized and unified leadership of the CCP as the most fundamental guarantee of the rule of law in China
2. implementing Xi Jinping's Thought on the socialist rule of law with Chinese characteristics
3. prioritizing the interests of the people in establishing the rule of law
4. promoting coordinated progress in law-based governance, unifying the rule of law with governing the Party according to regulations and combining the rule of law with the rule of virtue (e.g. virtuous leadership, social harmony, education and moral cultivation)
5. focusing on the prominent issues the Central Committee and people are concerned about, promoting the modernization of the national governance system and capacity and enhancing effectiveness
6. considering national circumstances or characteristics when establishing the rule of law, while considering Western experiences when appropriate

The overall objectives are:

1. By 2025, China should strengthen the institutional framework for the rule of law, establish a more comprehensive socialist legal system with Chinese characteristics (with the Constitution at its core), create a more efficient judicial system and enhance the application of internal party regulations.

2. By 2035, China will have established a socialist rule-of-law system with Chinese characteristics. Under this system, the state, government, and society will operate under the rule of law. People's rights to equal participation and development will be fully guaranteed. The national governance system and governance capabilities will be modernized.

Outline for the Implementation of Market Supervision under the Rule of Law (2021–2025) 《法治市场监管建设实施纲要（2021–2025年）》

This Outline was issued by the State Administration for Market Regulation on 13 December 2021, with the goal of establishing a well-defined, efficient, and law-based market regulation system that supports high-quality economic development by 2025.

- **Guiding Principles:**
 - Upholding the leadership of the Communist Party of China
 - Ensuring scientific, democratic, and law-based governance
 - Promoting fairness, justice, and transparency in market regulation
- **Key Objectives:**
 - **Legal Framework:** improving the legal system for market regulation, including laws on anti-monopoly, intellectual property, and consumer protection
 - **Enforcement:** strengthening law enforcement and supervision to ensure compliance and address violations effectively
 - **Innovation:** utilizing modern technologies like big data and AI to enhance regulatory capabilities
 - **Public Participation:** increasing public awareness and participation in market regulation
 - **International Cooperation:** aligning with international standards and improving cooperation with other countries